

PAPER • OPEN ACCESS

The feasibility study of the solar heat pump combined system for the production of hot water in Laos

To cite this article: Xayalak vilaida *et al* 2025 *IOP Conf. Ser.: Earth Environ. Sci.* **1511** 012003

View the [article online](#) for updates and enhancements.

You may also like

- [Atmospheric extinction coefficients and night sky brightness at Bosscha Observatory](#)
M Yusuf, H I Arwinata, T Perhati et al.
- [Laser-generation of focused acoustic vortex with Archimedean spiral optoacoustic surfaces](#)
Yujun Zeng, Wenyu Li, Weiwei Kan et al.
- [Effect of various nitrogen rates on MR303 rice yield performance and NDVI spectral reflectance](#)
S Shafiq, D E Pebrian, I Rakibe et al.

UNITED THROUGH SCIENCE & TECHNOLOGY

 The Electrochemical Society
Advancing solid state & electrochemical science & technology

**248th
ECS Meeting**
Chicago, IL
October 12-16, 2025
Hilton Chicago

**Science +
Technology +
YOU!**

**Register by
September 22
to save \$\$**

REGISTER NOW

The feasibility study of the solar heat pump combined system for the production of hot water in Laos

Xayalak vilaida^{1*}, Sengratry kythavone¹, Khamphone Nanthavong¹, Ohgaki Hideaki²

¹Department Mechanical Engineering, National University of Laos, Vientiane Capital, Lao PDR

²Institute of Advanced Energy, Kyoto University, Kyoto 6110011, Japan

*E-mail: x.vilaida@nuol.edu.la

Abstract. This study investigates the sustainability of solar collectors and heat pump systems for the production of sustainable hot water. The flat-plate solar collector with a single glass panel, copper tubes and black absorbers was tested in a size of 4 m² at different water flow rates (15 L/min, 17.5 L/min, 20 L/min) to 200 L. The 3,300W heat pump is equipped with a 25-plate heat exchanger and 370W water pump. The optimal flow rate at the time of heating was determined at 17 litres per minute. This rate achieved a thermal pump efficiency of 5.1%, which allowed water to heat up to 50°C in 24 minutes and cost 1,400 LAK. The system can produce water up to 50 °C with a capacity of 800 litres. Comparing economics to conventional coil water heaters, the system's initial cost (15,234,500 LAK, 9,566,000 LAK) is higher, but offers significant energy savings (81.4% annual savings), a five-year repayment period, and 31.8% Internal Rate of Return (IRR). Despite initial investments, this system offers promising options for efficient and sustainable production of hot water.

1. Introduction

Laos is increasingly adopting solar energy and solar hot water systems to enhance its energy sustainability. The country has initiated several projects, including solar water pumps and hybrid systems, to cater to rural communities and agricultural needs. For instance, a study focused on optimizing solar PV/T boosted heat pumps for hot water generation at the Kai Nakorn Hotel demonstrated significant reductions in electricity consumption, showcasing the potential for solar technology in commercial applications [1]. Additionally, the Lao government aims to diversify energy sources, targeting a 30% share from renewables by 2025, which includes expanding solar energy initiatives. A comprehensive review of solar water heating systems (SWHS) in the Middle East has revealed their technical and economic viability. The analysis focused on payback periods, CO₂ emission reductions, and system configurations across various incentive frameworks. The findings suggest that SWHS can effectively address regional energy challenges while also revealing both opportunities and obstacles to widespread adoption [2]. Hybrid systems that combine parabolic trough solar collectors with auxiliary electrical heaters have been proposed to ensure a consistent hot water supply. These hybrid solutions demonstrate lower levelized costs compared to conventional electrical heaters [3]. Recent studies have also explored the feasibility and performance of combined solar and heat pump systems for heating

and hot water generation. These hybrid systems have been shown to increase energy efficiency and reliability compared to standalone technologies [4;5]. Various configurations, including parallel, series, and preheating modes, have been investigated, with performance heavily influenced by factors such as solar radiation intensity and ambient temperature [6]. In Mediterranean climates, for instance, solar thermal systems integrated with water-water heat pumps have outperformed traditional geothermal or conventional heat pump systems [7]. Economic analyses of residential photovoltaic installations indicate high financial viability; one study found a system covering 93% of a household's annual energy consumption with a favourable Net Present Value and satisfactory Internal Rate of Return. The investment showed a discounted payback period of approximately twelve years, providing not only economic benefits but also significant energy independence by insulating households from volatile market prices [8]. Moreover, studies on photovoltaic heat pump water heaters have demonstrated substantial economic and environmental advantages. These systems can reduce non-renewable energy consumption by 79% and CO₂ emissions by 82%, with an annualized cost of approximately €337 over 25 years [9]. This study explores solar-assisted heat pump water heaters in energy-limited regions, revealing a predictive performance model with over 80% of system conditions exceeding baseline efficiency, offering strategic recommendations for solar energy optimization [10]. Solar-assisted heat pump systems for domestic hot water generation offer significant energy savings and environmental benefits compared to conventional heating methods. These hybrid systems can reduce energy consumption by up to 56.6% [11]. Economic analyses demonstrate cost savings of up to 46.8% over baseline heating systems [12]. The optimal configuration depends on factors such as location, system size, and demand patterns. For instance, a 12-panel photovoltaic-thermal array was found most economically viable for a UK household, covering 30% of electrical and 80% of hot water demands [13]. A dual-source heat pump assisted solar evacuated tube water heater system integrated with sunspace demonstrates significant energy efficiency in cold regions, achieving a 51.6% solar heating fraction, 46.0% solar heat collection efficiency, and reducing CO₂ emissions by 14,232.4 kg, with a dynamic payback period of 6.78 years and potential for accelerated economic viability through clean energy heating policies [14]. Despite higher initial investment costs associated with these advanced systems, they generally provide lower recurring yearly expenses and attractive payback periods. This positions them as promising alternatives for sustainable domestic water heating solutions. As Laos continues to invest in renewable energy infrastructure, the integration of solar technologies will play a crucial role in achieving its sustainability goals while addressing the challenges posed by climate change and rising energy demands.

2. System description

The Solar-Heat Pump Combined System for hot water generation is a solution that integrates solar thermal collectors with heat pump technology to provide efficient and sustainable hot water. This hybrid system captures solar energy through solar collectors, which convert sunlight into thermal energy. The collected heat is transferred to a heat transfer fluid that circulates through the system, heating water in a storage tank. This setup allows for the utilization of free solar energy, particularly during sunny periods, minimizing reliance on conventional energy sources.

In addition to solar collectors, the system incorporates a heat pump that serves as a secondary heat source. The heat pump extracts ambient thermal energy from the surrounding ambient temperature when solar radiation is insufficient, such as during cloudy days or at night. By employing a refrigeration cycle, the heat pump efficiently raises the temperature of the water

supply, ensuring that hot water demands are met consistently throughout the day. The combination of these two technologies enhances the overall efficiency of the system, allowing it to operate effectively under varying climatic conditions.

The buffer tank, which stores heated water from both the solar collectors and the heat pump. This tank helps manage fluctuations in hot water demand and optimizes the performance of each component by allowing them to operate independently when necessary. A control system monitors temperatures and manages operations, ensuring that solar energy is prioritized whenever available, as illustrated in Figure 1 and Figure 2.

Figure 1 systematic of the solar water generator

Figure 2 Operating Cycle Schematic of an Integrated Solar Water Heating and Heat Pump System

3. Materials and methods

3.1 Experimental procedure

This research involves a comprehensive experimental approach to the production of hot water using both passive and active solar energy systems. The first phase of the experiment focuses on utilizing natural solar energy through passive methods, where solar panels are connected in both series and parallel configurations. This setup allows for natural circulation of

water in the passive system, while the active system incorporates a circulation pump to enhance water flow.

In the second phase, we explore the integration of a heat pump in conjunction with a Plate Heat Exchanger condenser, which serves as an efficient medium for transferring heat to the water. This combination aims to maximize heat absorption and improve overall efficiency in hot water production. Additionally, we will investigate the impact of varying water flow rates on the system's performance, specifically targeting optimal temperature achievement and minimizing the time required for effective hot water generation. Through these experiments, we aim to identify the most efficient configurations and operational parameters for maximizing hot water production using renewable energy sources.

3.2 In a solar collector operating at steady-state, the rate of radiation absorbed at any given moment is equal to the sum of the rate of useful heat transfer and the rate of heat loss from the absorbing surface. This relationship can be expressed mathematically as the following equation: τ is the emission Factor and α absorption factor, I_T is the total solar radiation intensity incident on the collector, A_c is the collector area the useful energy output, T_p is the Surface temperature of the solar collector, T_a is the ambient air temperature. \dot{Q}_{coll} is the useful heat transfer rate from the solar collector, F_R is the heat removal factor, C_f is the specific heat capacity of the fluid, U_L is the Overall heat loss coefficient of the solar collector, η_{coll} is the efficiency of the solar collector.

$$(\tau\alpha)_e I_T A_c = \dot{Q}_{coll} + U_L A_c (T_p - T_a) \quad (1)$$

$$\dot{Q}_{coll} = \dot{m}_f C_f (T_{fo} - T_{fi}) \quad (2)$$

$$\dot{Q}_{coll} = (\tau\alpha)_e I_T A_c - U_L A_c (T_p - T_a) \quad (3)$$

$$\dot{Q}_{coll} = F_R (\tau\alpha)_e I_T A_c - F_R U_L A_c (T_p - T_a) \quad (4)$$

$$\eta_{coll} = \frac{\dot{Q}_{coll}}{I_T A_c} = F_R (\tau\alpha)_e - F_R U_L \frac{(T_p - T_a)}{I_T} \quad (5)$$

3.3 For the heat pump system utilized in this hot water production setup, the compressor operates on a 380V electrical power supply and uses R-22 refrigerant. The design of the heat pump system will be calculated based on these specific compressor specifications to ensure optimal performance and efficiency in generating hot water. The calculations will account for the compressor's capacity, the refrigerant characteristics, and the overall system requirements to achieve effective heating outcomes. \dot{W}_C is the power required by the compressor, \dot{m}_{R22} is mass flow rate of the working fluid through the compressor, enthalpy difference ($h_{out} - h_{in}$) across the compressor, \dot{Q}_{Cond} is the heat transfer rate through the condenser, \dot{Q}_{Evap} is Heat transfer rate through the evaporator, ($h_{out} = h_{in}$) is the enthalpy through an expansion valve, COP is the Coefficient of Performance, ε is the Condenser Effectiveness, U is the overall heat transfer coefficient, C_{min} C_{max} are the minimum specific heat and maximum specific heat, UA is the total thermal conductance of a system, \dot{m}_w is the mass flow rate of water, Δx is the thickness of the material, h_1 is the convective heat transfer coefficient.

$$\dot{W}_C = \dot{m}_{R22} (h_{out} - h_{in}) \quad (6)$$

$$\dot{Q}_{Cond} = \dot{m}_R (h_{out} - h_{in}) \quad (7)$$

$$\dot{Q}_{Evap} = \dot{m}_R (h_{in} - h_{out}) \quad (8)$$

$$\text{COP} = \frac{\dot{Q}_{\text{cond}}}{W_{\text{Comp}}} \quad (9)$$

$$\varepsilon = \frac{T_{\text{wo}} - T_{\text{wi}}}{T_{\text{Cond}} - T_{\text{wi}}} \quad (10)$$

$$UA = m_w C_{pw} \frac{T_{\text{Cond}} - T_{\text{wi}}}{T_{\text{Cond}} - T_{\text{wi}}} \quad (11)$$

$$\varepsilon = f\left(\frac{UA}{C_{\text{min}}}, \frac{C_{\text{min}}}{C_{\text{max}}}\right) \quad (12)$$

$$U = \frac{1}{1/h_1 A + \Delta x/kA + 1/h_2 A} \quad (13)$$

3.4 The incorporation of a Plate Heat Exchanger (PHE) in this solar-heat pump system presents an opportunity to further optimize heat transfer efficiency. The PHE, as a newly developed technology, has the potential to improve the overall thermal performance of the system, delivering more effective heat exchange and enhanced hot water generation. A_p is the effective area, Φ is the coefficient of heat exchanger, W_p is the width and L_p is the length of heat exchanger, $LMTD$ is the Logarithmic Mean Temperature Difference, ΔT_1 and ΔT_2 are the temperature difference at inlet or outlet, t_p is the thickness of plate, k_p is the thermal conductivity of aluminium plate.

$$A_p = \Phi \cdot W_p \cdot L_p \quad (14)$$

$$\dot{Q}_{\text{cond}} = U \cdot A \cdot LMTD \quad (15)$$

$$LMTD = \frac{\Delta T_1 - \Delta T_2}{\ln\left(\frac{\Delta T_1}{\Delta T_2}\right)} \quad (16)$$

$$U = \frac{1}{\frac{1}{h_{\text{hot}}} + \frac{t_p}{k_p} + \frac{1}{h_{\text{cold}}}} \quad (17)$$

3.5 The selected compressor is a closed-type model that operates with a three-phase alternating current electric motor, chosen based on the specifications provided in the manufacturer's manual. I is the electrical current, U is the local electrical voltage, $\text{Cos}\theta$ is the power factor at 90° . Re is the Reynolds number, G_c is the mass flux, D_e is the effective diameter of the pipe, μ is the dynamic viscosity of the fluid, b is the dimension of the flow channel, ϕ is the correction factor, Nu Nusselt number, h_{cold} is the convective heat transfer coefficient for the cold fluid, k is the thermal conductivity of fluid, h_{hot} is The convective heat transfer coefficient for the hot fluid, ρ_f is The density of the fluid, is the density of the vapor, h_{fg} is The enthalpy of vaporization (latent heat) of the fluid, k_f is The thermal conductivity of the fluid, T_{sat} is the saturation temperature of the fluid at a given pressure, T_s is The surface temperature of the solid boundary in contact with the fluid. L is the length of plate. The power of the compressor can be calculated using the following method:

$$\text{COP} = \frac{\dot{Q}_{\text{cond}}}{P_{\text{Compressor}}} \quad (18)$$

$$P_{\text{Compressor}} = IUC\text{os}\theta\sqrt{3} \quad (19)$$

$$\text{Re} = \frac{G_c D_e}{\mu} \quad (20)$$

$$D_e = \frac{2b}{\phi} \quad (21)$$

$$G_c = \frac{\dot{m}}{bW_p} \quad (22)$$

$$\text{Nu} = \frac{h_{\text{cold}} \cdot D_e}{k} \quad (23)$$

$$h_{\text{hot}} = 0.943 \left[\frac{g \rho_f (\rho_f - \rho_v) h_{fg} k_f^3}{\mu (T_{\text{sat}} - T_s) L} \right]^{1/4} \quad (24)$$

3.6 In a scenario without thermal stratification within the hot water receiver and accumulator tank. Q_s is the sensible heat transfer, Q_{cond} is the heat transfer due to conduction, Q_{load} is thermal load, Q_{loss} is heat losses from the system, $\left(\frac{dT_s}{dt}\right)$ is the rate of change of temperature with respect to time at the surface. the water temperature can be characterized through an energy balance equation as follows:

$$Q_s = Q_{\text{cond}} - Q_{\text{load}} - Q_{\text{loss}} \quad (25)$$

$$Q_s = Q_{\text{cond}} = (m_w C_w)_s \left(\frac{dT_s}{dt}\right) \quad (26)$$

$$T_s^{t+\Delta T} = T_s^t + \frac{\Delta t}{m_w C_{pw}} Q_{\text{cond}} \quad (27)$$

The parameters shown in the **Table 1** are critical for the design and optimization of the integrated solar water heating and heat pump system. They help determine key factors such as heat transfer, thermal efficiency, and system dimensions.

Table 1. Design Parameters for Integrated Solar Water Heating and Heat Pump System

No.	Items	Symbol	Value
1	Specific heating value	C_p	4.187 kJ/kg°C
2	Thermal conductivity of copper	k	390 W/m. °C
3	Plate spacing	b	3 mm
4	coefficient of heat exchanger	Φ	1.15- 1.25
5	Standard gravity	g	9.81 m/s ²
6	Thickness of plate	t_p	0.06 mm
7	Thermal conductivity of aluminium plate	k_p	17 W/m°C
8	Lenth of plate	L	0.52 m

3.7 The hot water generator system is designed to fulfil a household's daily hot water needs, with thermal performance specifications based on raising the water temperature from an initial 30°C to a final 50°C, validated through detailed usage scenario analyses and storing solar-heated water during the day for nighttime use. C_c is the Capital Cost, P is the present value of the investment, i is the interest rate, n is the total number of payment periods, C_T is the Total Cost, C_e is the Energy Cost, C_s is the Salvage Cost, SPP is the Simple Payback Period, NPV is the Net Present Value, NCF_n is the Net Cash Flow in period, TIC is the Total Initial Cost.

$$C_c = P \left[\frac{i(1+i)^n}{(1+i)^n - 1} \right] \quad (28)$$

$$C_m = iP \quad (29)$$

$$C_e = (\text{Day of the Year}) \times (\text{Energy a day}) \times \text{energy cost} \quad (30)$$

$$C_s = P \left[\frac{i}{(1+i)^n - 1} \right] \quad (31)$$

$$C_T = C_c + C_m + C_e + C_s \quad (32)$$

$$SPP = \frac{\text{First Cost}}{\text{Cost Saving}} \quad (33)$$

$$NPV = \sum_{i=1}^n \left[\frac{NCF_n}{(1+i)^n} - TIC \right] = 0 \quad (34)$$

The parameters in **Table 2** outline the key economic and operational assumptions for designing and evaluating the integrated solar water heating and heat pump system. These factors, including system lifetime, energy costs, financing, maintenance, and capacity, are crucial for assessing the system's overall feasibility and performance.

Table 2. Consolidated Economic Main Assumptions

Hot water Generator system		
Items	Value	Unit
Useful life	7	years
Operating time	365	days/year
Energy price	710	LAK/kWh
Interest rate	7	%
Scrap value	10	%
Maintenance cost	2	%/year
Family size	5	people
Storage tank	200	L
Electric Heater		
Power input	4.4	kW

4. Results and discussion

4.1 Solar energy system

The experimental results indicate that the intensity of solar radiation varies between 505.2 W/m² and 1,389.1 W/m². This range is sufficiently strong to facilitate effective hot water production. The experiment was conducted over a period from 08:30 AM to 05:30 PM. In this study, solar panels were configured in two distinct arrangements: series and parallel. This dual setup allows for a comprehensive analysis of the performance and efficiency of the solar panels under varying conditions.

The experimental results reveal that when solar panels are connected in series, a water flow rate of 17 L/min achieves a maximum water temperature of 80.1°C in the tank within just 2 hours. This performance is superior compared to higher flow rates of 20 L/min and 15 L/min, which resulted in tank temperatures of 69.2°C, 80.1°C, and 80.0°C, respectively. These findings are illustrated in Figure 3.

Experiment at 15 L/min

Figure 3 Correlation Between Solar Radiation Intensity and Temperature Fluctuations
 In the case of connecting solar panels in parallel, the results indicate that a flow rate of 17 L/min achieves a maximum water temperature of 80°C. In contrast, a flow rate of 15 L/min results in maximum tank temperatures of 69.2°C and 65°C, respectively. Additionally, the lower flow rates require a longer time to reach these temperatures, as illustrated in Figure 4.

Experiment at 20 L/min

Experiment at 17 L/min

Experiment at 15 L/min

Figure 4 Correlation Between Solar Radiation Intensity and Temperature Fluctuations
 Additionally, the effectiveness of using a heat pump as an auxiliary heating source was tested during periods without sunlight, such as during thunderstorms, rain, or at night. This evaluation was conducted at the optimal flow rate identified in previous experiments. Evaluation of Heat Pump Performance as an Auxiliary System. Additionally, the effectiveness of using a heat pump as an auxiliary heating source was tested during periods without sunlight, such as during thunderstorms, rain, or at night. This evaluation was conducted at the optimal flow rate identified

in previous experiments. Three different flow rates were tested: 15 L/min, 17 L/min, and 20 L/min. The results showed that at a flow rate of 17 L/min, the time required to heat the water in the tank from an initial temperature of 31°C to 50°C was 24 minutes. In comparison, at flow rates of 15 L/min and 20 L/min, the heating times were 30 minutes and 25 minutes, respectively.

Based on these findings, a flow rate of 17 L/min will be selected for future experiments as it provides the shortest heating time for producing hot water, as illustrated in Figure 5. In this experiment focused on producing hot water using solar energy, a heat pump was employed as an auxiliary system. Given the climatic conditions in Laos, characterized by ample sunlight intensity and hours of sunshine, this setup is particularly suitable for generating hot water for bathing and various household tasks, making it ideal for small apartments. During the day, the solar system functions as the primary hot water generator. However, at night or during periods of insufficient sunlight, the heat pump serves as a backup heating source. This dual approach ensures a consistent supply of hot water regardless of weather conditions.

Figure 5 Correlation Between Solar Radiation Intensity and Temperature Fluctuations

4.2 Heat pump system

The experimental results indicate that each flow rate 15 L/min, 17 L/min, and 20 L/min requires a distinct amount of time to heat the water, as illustrated in Figure 6. This variation highlights the impact of flow rate on heating efficiency and time. At a flow rate of 17 L/min, the optimal time to heat the water in the tank was recorded, taking just 24 minutes to raise the temperature from 31°C to 50°C. In contrast, at a flow rate of 15 L/min, the heating process took longer, requiring 30 minutes to achieve the same temperature increase, as shown in Figure 6.

Experiment at 15 l/min

Figure 6 Relationship Between Electric Current and Storage Tank Temperature Over Time

The experiment revealed that heating water starting from 20°C, which simulates winter conditions, required a significantly longer time. Specifically, it took 40 minutes to raise the temperature from 20°C to 50°C. This extended heating duration highlights the challenges associated with warming colder water.

Figure 7 Hot Water Generator System Parameters for Winter Simulation

In the experiment involving the use of hot water, the water in the tank was initially heated to 50°C. After reaching this temperature, the hot water was released from the tank, allowing cold water to flow in. The experiment utilized the optimal flow rate of 17 L/min. During this process, it was observed that the pump operated continuously, while both the current and pressure gradually decreased until they stabilized, as illustrated in Figure 8.

Figure 8 Experiment Utilizing Hot Water

4.3 Economic results

Comparing the annual electricity costs, the solar hot water system with a heat pump auxiliary demonstrates a significantly lower expense of 265,684 LAK, compared to the electric coil heater hot water system's cost of 1,425,325 LAK. The analysis reveals that the electric heater hot water

system's electricity costs are substantially higher, approximately 5.36 times more expensive than the solar alternative, despite the solar system's higher initial investment, as shown in **Table 3**.

Table 3. Compare the annual costs of the two hot water generation systems

Items	Propose system		Electric heater system	
	LAK	USD	LAK	USD
Initial cost	2,826,811	257	1,775,002	161
Energy cost	265,684	24	1,425,325	129.5
Maintenance cost	304,690	27.7	191,320	17
Scrap value	176,039	16	110,538	10
Total annual charge	3,573,225	324.7	3,502,185	317.5

5. Conclusions

Based on the comprehensive feasibility study of the solar hot water system with a heat pump auxiliary in Vientiane Capital, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. System Design and Capacity:

The solar hot water system was meticulously engineered for a five-person household, precisely delivering 200 liters of heated water daily while reliably sustaining a minimum temperature of 50°C through its strategically configured 4 m² solar collection array.

2. Solar Radiation Performance:

The system exhibits robust performance across solar radiation levels from 614.3 W/m² to 1,389.1 W/m², showcasing its exceptional adaptability in solar energy conversion.

3. Heating Configuration Optimization:

The solar hot water system demonstrated varying heating performance across series plate and parallel flow configurations, with the series connection achieving faster heating from 30°C to 50°C in 1 hour and 50 minutes, compared to the parallel flow configuration's 2-hour heating cycle, both maintained at a consistent 17 L/min flow rate.

4. Heat Pump Performance:

The solar hot water system efficiently heats 200 liters from 30°C to 50°C in just 24 minutes, consuming only 1.6 kWh and incurring a minimal production cost of 1,400 LAK.

5. Economic Viability:

The solar hot water system delivers significant economic advantages, with up to 81.36% annual electricity cost reduction, a 5-year payback period, and a robust 31.83% Internal Rate of Return.

The solar hot water system with a heat pump auxiliary proves to be a technologically advanced and financially attractive renewable energy solution. It offers significant energy savings, reduced operational costs, and contributes to sustainable household energy management in Vientiane Capital's climatic conditions.

References

- [1] Mungkhaly, P., Polvongsri, S., & Mongkon, S. (2022). An optimization study of hot water generation from solar PV/T boosted heat pump: Case study of Kai Nakorn Hotel, Vientiane Capital, Laos PDR. *RMUTI Journal of Science and Technology*, 15(2), May-August 2022.
- [2] Dehghan, M., Pfeiffer, C. F., Rakhshani, E., & Bakhshi-Jafarabadi, R. (2021). A review on techno-economic assessment of solar water heating systems in the Middle East. *Energies*, 14(16), 4944. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en14164944>

- [3] Jaramillo, O., Aguilar, J. O., Castrejón-García, R., Venegas-Reyes, E., & Sosa-Montemayor, F. (2013). Parabolic trough concentrators for hot water generation: Comparison of the levelized cost of production. *Journal of Renewable and Sustainable Energy*, 5(2), 023114. <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4795402>
- [4] Jeong, Y., Yu, M., & Nam, Y. (2017). Feasibility study of a heating, cooling and domestic hot water system combining a photovoltaic-thermal system and a ground source heat pump. *Energies*, 10(8), Article 1234. <https://doi.org/10.3390/en10081234>
- [5] Ahmad, M., Eftekhari, M., & Steffen, T. (2012, October 15). Model development of a solar system combined with heat pump [Paper presentation]. International Conference on Automation and Computing.
- [6] Long, J., Xia, K., Zhong, H., & Lu, H. (2021). Study on energy-saving operation of a combined heating system of solar hot water and air source heat pump. *Energy Conversion and Management*, 234, Article 113956. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enconman.2021.113956>
- [7] Moia Pol, A., Martínez Moll, V., Alomar Barceló, M., & Pujol Nadal, R. (2012). Solar and heat pump systems: An analysis of several combinations in Mediterranean areas. *Engineering, Environmental Science*. <https://hrcak.srce.hr/file/144634>
- [8] Ozdarski, W. T., Witkowska-Dąbrowska, M., & De Jesus, I. M. (2021). Feasibility study of the use of renewable energy sources in households. *Olsztyn Economic Journal*, 16(4), 375-392. <https://doi.org/10.31648/oej.6865>
- [9] Aguilar, F., Crespi-Llorens, D., & Quiles, P. V. (2019). Environmental benefits and economic feasibility of a photovoltaic assisted heat pump water heater. *Solar Energy*, 193, 20-30. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.solener.2019.09.032>
- [10] Liu, M., He, Y., Zhang, H., Su, H., & Zhang, Z. (2020). The feasibility of solar thermal-air source heat pump water heaters in renewable energy shortage regions. *Energy*, 197, Article 117189. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.energy.2020.117189>
- [11] Jin, X., You, S., Huang, G., & Lai, A. C. K. (2023). Techno-economic assessment of the solar-assisted heat pump latent heat thermal energy storage system for water heating. *Energy and Buildings*, 301, Article 113657. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.enbuild.2023.113657>
- [12] Okandeji Alexander, O. A., Oshevire, P., & Oshevire Patrick (2022, November 1). Hybrid solar/heat pump system for water heating in Nigeria: Techno-economic assessment [Paper presentation]. 5th Information Technology for Education and Development (ITED). IEEE.
- [13] Obalanlege, M. A., Xu, J., Markides, C. N., & Mahmoudi, Y. (2022). Techno-economic analysis of a hybrid photovoltaic-thermal solar-assisted heat pump system for domestic hot water and power generation. *Renewable Energy*, 196, 720-736. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2022.07.044>
- [14] Zhai, P., Li, J., Lei, T., Li, R., & Novakovic, V. (2024). Application of heat pump assisted solar evacuated tube water heater operated within passive solar house in severe cold region. *Renewable Energy*, 237(A), Article 121629. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.renene.2024.121629>